

<https://dh-ignite.org>

DH-IGNITE

Connect - Learn - Grow

Schedule of events

Kwa-Zulu Natal

19 & 20 October '22

- UKZN
- UNIZULU
- MUT
- DUT

COMPLETED

Western Cape

8 - 10 March '23

- UWC
- UCT
- SU
- CPUT

COMPLETED

NEXT →

Central/West Region

23 - 25 August '23

- VUT
- NWU
- TUT
- UP
- WITS
- UJ
- UP
- SMU
- CUT
- UFS
- SPU
- CSIR
- HSRC

Eastern Cape

End of Nov/Early Dec
In collaboration with DHASA

- WSU
- UFS
- RU
- NMU

COMING SOON

North/East Region

7 - 9 February '24

- UNIVEN
- UMP
- UL

COMING SOON

science & innovation

Department:
Science and Innovation
REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

Creating a welcoming learning environment

Through DH-IGNITE, we created opportunities for researchers, students and practitioners to learn about each others' work, ideas, challenges, and solutions. The interactive programme included sessions on research infrastructure, data, learning opportunities, regional DH projects, interdisciplinary collaboration, and even chatGPT.

Connect

Over 200 researchers, students, and librarians from Kwa-Zulu Natal and the Western Cape have participated virtually or in person in DH-IGNITE events in these regions.

Learn

More than 50 presenters from 22 institutions presented talks, lightning talks, panel discussions, and workshops

Grow

"Attending DH-IGNITE [...] has been a valuable opportunity to acquire new knowledge, network with colleagues, and discover innovative tools and methods to enhance my work."

Nokuthula Ndlovu (CPUT)

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What does the community say?

DH-IGNITE KZN

Great initiative, awesome and insightful conference. Looking forward to being part of this community.

DH-IGNITE Western Cape

The organising team - helpful, energetic, enthusiastic. The structure with changing speakers and different voices made it stimulating. It was not possible to get bored. I think that it was also great that it was hybrid. Having the the whole A/V crew was also great. So professional.

DH-IGNITE Western Cape

Perhaps a session on support for DH, e.g. with librarians, research office staff, etc. sharing their experiences.

DH-IGNITE KZN

Please include an extra morning or afternoon event with hands on training

DH-IGNITE Western Cape

Thank you for a super well organised event and the hard work to take care of everyone so well.

DH-IGNITE Western Cape

Thank you for the opportunity to attend DH-Ignite; I connected (met new people), learned new things, and grew. I am glad I chose to attend in person.

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